

Real versus expected market value creation (based on Warsaw Stock Exchange WIG30 companies)

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Submitted: 24 April 2025. Accepted: 6 August 2025.

Suggested citation: Kaczmarek J., Nández Alonso S.L. (2025), Real versus expected market value creation (based on Warsaw Stock Exchange WIG30 companies), *Bank i Kredyt*, 56(6), 673–702, DOI: 10.5604/01.3001.0055.4547.

Abstract

The purpose of this article is to assess the adequacy of excess market value added to equity as an external measure of company value creation in terms of meeting shareholders' expectations. Panel research covered 30 WIG30 index companies on the Warsaw Stock Exchange in 2017–2024. Mathematical statistics tools, a density measure, and a taxonomic measure of similarity were used to evaluate the results.

Three hypotheses were tested. First, the excess measure has been shown not to distort market information and to be suitable for assessing the effectiveness of value creation, taking into account shareholders' expectations. Second, insufficient value creation has been demonstrated, which results in a negative assessment of value-based management, both in terms of its effectiveness and its efficiency. Third, the value creation profiles of companies are not similar in terms of rank position with respect to the strength of creation, its volatility, and its risk – both overall and broken down by activity.

The value of this rare research is the objective way in which it assesses company value creation versus shareholder expectations and the application of its methodology in expectations-based management.

Keywords: excess value, expectations-based management, value creation

JEL: G32

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1. Introduction

1.1. The nature of value creation models

Without entering into a broader theoretical discourse, in practice it is company value and its creation that provide a universal and comprehensive measure of company performance (Copeland, Koller, Murrin 2020, pp. 20–27). Assessing this value is a domain usually reserved for shareholders, but if value for shareholders is to grow, the value for stakeholders must grow too (Rappaport 2006). Such value is therefore a tangible expression of the realisation of their expectations and, more broadly, the development of the company (Srivastava, Shervani, Fahey 1998).

This relationship does not invalidate the discussion about the attrition model of shareholders and stakeholders. The reason is not only the difference in objectives and the multiplicity of parties (Tirole 2001). A practical obstacle is the lack of a measure of stakeholder wealth (Bebchuk, Tallarita 2022). Therefore, despite the criticism of an excessive focus on short-term value creation and purely financial rewards, the shareholder model is still common (Bradford, Shapiro 2021). It is on this foundation that the concept of value based management (VBM) is built (Chari, Mohanty 2009).

Undoubtedly, the stakeholders model is fostered by the development of the concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR), or sustainable development (Lidgreen et al. 2016). They directly target creating shared value (CSV) (Porter, Kramer 2011). Complications arise when the environment and community (setting) become ‘mute’ shareholders and are to be included in the measurement of value. In support of the stakeholders model, institutional investors play a central role (Dressler, Mugerma 2023), prompting pro-ESG actions. Although its impact on financial outcomes has been demonstrated (Dangelico, Pujari 2010), the measures of these outcomes, including value created, are still the same (York 2009).

A mitigation against the polarity of value creation models is brought about by the proposal of an ‘illuminated’ VBM, which assumes complementarity of interests and value creation for stakeholders and shareholders (Cwynar, Cwynar 2007, pp. 13–14). This proposition, developed in expectations-based management (EBM), has an additional key dimension in terms of its ability to ensure sustainable value creation (Fijorek et al. 2021). The prerequisite, however, is both the generation of added value and its realisation. This realisation takes place, among other things, through share appreciation, as discussed in the next section.

As shown above, financial measures of value creation are still a common and adequate basis for measuring value creation. This statement underpins this article as an epistemological core. This is related to the objects of study, i.e. listed companies, for which value creation as a financial objective is a categorical imperative.

The measurement of value creation has undergone an intensive evolution, now relying on market measures, mainly market value added (MVA) as an external measure. It expresses an objective, market-based measurement, representing not the company’s performance, but the shareholders’ opinion on it.

1.2. Premises, objectives, and research hypotheses

This last observation is valuable, but are there shortcomings in the way the MVA measures value? In fact, from the broadest perspective, the verification of the effects of corporate development is

the assessment of the execution of stakeholders' expectations. This approach, however, raises doubts whether managers, by pursuing a particular strategy of managing company value, and thus clearly belonging to the group of stakeholders themselves (Sakawa, Watanabel 2020), sufficiently ensure shareholders' expectations. It can be questioned whether MVA is a measure that provides an appropriate/reliable basis for assessing value creation from the shareholders' perspective alone. Does it realistically assess and express their level of expectations (i.e. minimum return covering the cost of capital, an at least similar and preferably above-average return on investment in the shares of a given company)? The key in this respect is how to measure value creation for shareholders.

The concerns expressed above form the basis for the research in the article. The research problem addressed is the internal measurement of the company's value creation in terms of meeting shareholders' expectations. Therefore, the first objective of the article is to evaluate the adequacy of the proposed modified measure in the form of excess market value added. Adequacy, in this case, means whether the proposed measure does not distort market information while being appropriate for use in assessing the effectiveness of shareholder value creation, taking into account shareholder expectations. The achievement of the first objective makes it possible to undertake two further objectives: the detection of above-average value creation and the formulation of a related classification of companies, as well as the assessment of the similarity of company profiles in terms of their ranking position resulting from the strength of value creation, the volatility of that position and the degree of risk – both overall and by activity.

The research in the article is conducted on the relationship in the domain of market value (company capitalisation) and market value added. The general assessment perspective adopted is the creation of value for shareholders, therefore, to their invested equity capital.

Concerning the objectives of the article, three research hypotheses are set as follows:

H1. Excess market value added to equity is positively, strongly, and statistically significantly correlated with changes in company capitalisation to a degree similar to increases in the market value added to equity.

H2. The degree of creation of market value added to equity is sufficient from the point of view of shareholders' expectations, i.e. it exceeds the minimum required rate of return on invested equity.

H3. Value creation profiles in terms of the market value added to equity and the excess market value added to equity are similar.

The realisation of the research objective and the verification of the formulated hypotheses took place under the conditions of the capital market in Poland. The panel research covered 30 companies with the highest capitalisation and market liquidity of shares (WIG30 index) on the Warsaw Stock Exchange (WSE). The study period is 2017–2024, with presentation of results following monthly periodisation.

2. Created value measurement vs. shareholders' expectations

In practice, the internal measurement of value created is equated with economic value added (EVA), developed as systemic value added (Magni 2003). In essence, it is the difference in the rate of return and the cost of capital multiplied by the capital invested, taking into account changes in the value of its equivalents and adjustments for result items that are not created from the use of operating assets

(O'Hanlon, Peasnell 2000). In contrast, external measurement is market value added (MVA) as the difference between market value and invested capital (Hillman, Keim 2001). In listed companies, market value is the company capitalisation. Hence, MVA is the difference between this capitalisation and equity. Both EVA and MVA are absolute measures, and a positive value means value added creation. It has been postulated that MVA is the sum of the net present value of an EVA series, obviously taking into account only equity and its cost.

In general, MVA as an opinion on performance expressed by the market applies only to listed companies and only to their entirety (not business units) (Nyiramahoro, Shooshina 2001), it treats the market capitalisation of a company as the only benefit to owners (no cash distributions to shareholders), it is an absolute measure and difficult to compare.

The main weakness of MVA is that it does not take into account shareholders' expectations of future value creation. Consequently, despite the creation of added value, achieving a return on investment below shareholders expectations results in a fall in share prices and vice versa – a return above expectations results in the share price increasing.

The reason lies in the difference between the understanding of company value creation and shareholder value creation (La Porta 1996). From shareholders' point of view, it is necessary both to generate added value and to realise it. This realisation is achieved, among other things, by increasing the value of the shares brought about by the achievement of results more favourable than expected by shareholders. The expected value is included in the market price of the share as the value of future growth.

Based on this criticism, a postulate was made about the necessary consideration of the difference between the real (achieved) value added and the one expected by shareholders. This means measuring excess market value added, which is undoubtedly a more restrictive criterion than market value added. At its core, excess market value added is a combination of two measurement routes, i.e. surplus return and value added. The result is excess residual income as the difference between real and expected annual economic profit, or, more broadly, also multi-year profit.

To date, empirical studies of value added have been conducted on equity (Perotti, Wagenhofer 2011) and bonds (Bosse, Wimmer, Philips 2013), also on emerging markets (Gilmore, Hayashi 2011) and the Far East (Nurwati, Ramdi 2013). These studies examined value creation but only using 'classic' value added measures (EVA, MVA). Additionally, the correlation was examined not for the expected shareholder value creation, but only between the resulting MVA and the performance of the companies (Quintiliani 2018). The relationship between MVA and EVA and their impact on the stock rate of return was also examined (Johan 2019). In view of the conditions of the Polish capital market, a study of surplus TSR and MVA for four companies in the fuel sector (Mikołajek-Gocejna 2010) can be mentioned, which showed a trend of destruction of values, without seeking relationships with other measures of value creation. Another relevant piece of research is a study of the relationship between the internal measures of EVA, DCF and the external measure of MVA (Kaczmarek 2018). It did not confirm the correlation searched in this regard. In turn, studies of IT and video game companies (Pilch 2021) have shown a non-relationship between 'classic' measures of value (MVA, TSR) and simple return ratios (EPS, ROA, ROE, ROIC).

Therefore, the deficit in how to measure the creation of market value added from the point of view of shareholders was recognised. Its essence is the simultaneous assessment of the effectiveness

and efficiency of value creation. Effectiveness is the achievement of positive market value added, and efficiency is the achievement of figures that are satisfactory to shareholders. This approach is provided by the excess value concept proposed in the article.

3. Research methods

Since MVA_E is the difference between Market Value to Equity (MV_E), or stock market capitalisation, and invested equity with equivalents (IC_E^C) – share capital, reserves and surplus less revaluation reserve and accumulated losses plus equivalents, e.g. adjustments for deferred tax reserve, inventory pricing reserve), positive value and value creation will occur when return on invested equity ($ROIC_E^C$) exceeds equity cost (ECC^C) (Pfeiffer 2004).

$$MVA_E = MV_E - IC_E^C; ROIC_E^C > ECC^C \rightarrow MVA_E > 0 \rightarrow \text{value creation} \quad (1)$$

Shareholder expectations can be accommodated in two ways: (1) by relativisation to rates of value creation in other investments, thus examining Superior Shareholder Return (SSR), which, however, does not ensure that the objectives of the article are met, (2) by comparison of the real return with the expected return, which brings excess return. When the expected return is expressed by equity cost, excess return is the rate of return that exceeds what was expected or predicted (e.g. by CAPM – Capital Asset Pricing Model).

This second way (Holler 2009; Mikołajek-Gocejna 2014) was used in the article to define the excess market value added to equity (MVA_{EN}). It is the difference between the expected value (MVA_{EP}) and the real value (MVA_{ER}). Thus, MVA_{EP} means the incremental MV_E over the minimum required rate of return on invested equity ($ROIC_E^C$), equivalent to the equity cost margin (ECC^C). This increment is reduced by invested equity (IC_E^C). A positive MVA_{EN} value means that excess value is achieved. It can be compared with the change in $dMVA_E$ (delta, value creation), but not with the absolute value of MVA_E .

$$MVA_{EP} = MV_{E,t-1} (1 + ECC_t^C) - IC_{E,t-1}^C; MVA_{EN} = MVA_{ER} - MVA_{EP} \quad (2)$$

$$MVA_{EN} > 0 \rightarrow \text{excess value} \quad (3)$$

As a comment, it should be added that proposing a modification towards a redundant EVA_E is not justified, as it still applies the above-mentioned criterion (its positive value implies a return higher than expected, determined by the cost of equity).

The research hypotheses defined in the introduction can be translated into the expected values of the correlational relationships studied:

If H1 were true, then the correlation for the associated correlation coefficients $r(MVA_{EN}; dMV_E)$ and $r(dMVA_E; dMV_E)$ should be very high;

If H2 were true, then the correlation $r(MVA_E; dMVA_{EP})$ should be almost full;

If H3 were true, then the measure of the similarity of value creation and risk profiles for $dMVA_E$ and MVA_{EN} should be close to unity.

3.1. Analytical tools

To verify hypothesis H1, it was necessary to use non-standard mathematical statistics tools. Williams test statistic (T_2) was applied for the equality of two related r-Pearson correlation coefficients (Meng, Rosenthal, Rubin 1992). Hypothesis H2 was verified using a test for a single r-Pearson correlation coefficient (degrees of correlation strength: < 0.1 faint; 0.1–0.3 weak; 0.3–0.5 average; 0.5–0.7 high; 0.7–0.9 very high; > 0.9 almost full). The critical level of significance was taken as $\alpha = 0.05$. A probability value (p-value) lower than α entitles one to proceed *ad hoc* as if the null hypothesis of no correlation had been rejected, which is the basis for accepting the alternative hypothesis of the existence of a correlation (Wasserstein, Lazar 2016; Hubbard, Bayarri 2012). In general, changes in stock market capitalisation with a stable share price, affecting the components of the value measures equally (e.g. merger, acquisition, spin-off), do not impact the direction and strength of the correlations studied. To verify hypothesis H3, the taxonomic measure of similarity (TMS) was used (Kolegowicz, Kaczmarek, Szymła 2022). It determines the difference in structures over time, simultaneously, in terms of two quantities, i.e. $dMVA_E$ and MVA_{EN} . The closer its value is to unity, the higher the similarity of the structures.

The average rank method was used in the ranking. The rule of thumb was to assign the lowest rank value to the highest value of the measure analysed at the given moment. For the time series, the average rank position (ARP) and the variability of rank position (VRP) were calculated, taking the standard deviation as the VRP measure. In principle, the ranking procedure eliminates the impact of outlier observations.

The density of sites (companies) was investigated using a density measure (DM) constructed for this purpose (Kaczmarek 2022). Its value corresponds to the area of the ellipse that covers the set of objects (companies) studied in the plane. A higher DM value indicates greater dispersion.

The required rate of return on invested equity ($ROIC_E^C$) was determined by the CAPM model (augmenting the risk-free rate by the product of the systemic risk measure ‘beta’ and the equity risk premium – ERP). Calculations were made individually for each company. The beta measure was calculated from the returns on company shares relative to the returns on the portfolio that makes up the WIG30 index (weekly rates, 2017–2024). Stock quotes, including splits, subscription rights, and dividends, were used. The ERP was calculated as the difference between the average annual return on the S&P 500 index and the average yield on 30-year US Treasury bonds (stepwise, for jumps in the time series). This was then enhanced by a country risk premium as the difference in yields on 10-year US and Polish government bonds.

3.2. Empirical data

The 2017–2024 panel study covered 30 companies from the Warsaw Stock Exchange WIG30 index, prevailing in the capitalisation of the stock market (39.4%). Their assets at the end of 2024 were PLN 3,031 bn and reached revenues of PLN 834 bn. They accumulated PLN 564 bn in equity, with a capitalisation value of PLN 571 bn. In terms of assets and capitalisation, finance companies (banking and insurance) predominate. In contrast, in terms of equity and sales, production companies (mining

and manufacturing) do. Commerce and hospitality companies rank third in terms of capitalisation. The characteristics of the companies studied have been provided in Table 3 (Appendix).

Data sources included emis.com, notoria.pl, gpw.pl, stockwatch.pl, and ekrs.ms.gov.pl. (commercial access). Regression-based imputation was used in completing the input data for the estimation of the value added, without significantly deforming the absolute values. The scope of value-added calculation adjustments has been limited to the information available in the financial statements. The results of the value-added measurement are presented for a monthly periodisation. The input periodic data are converted to an annual timeframe, and therefore the added value and related categories are cumulative figures.

4. Results

4.1. Value creation and its gap

Until 2019, the capitalisation of the companies surveyed (MV_E) was stable (annual average), with a lockdown period (2020), an attempted rebound in 2021 and a rapid one from 2023 onward. The final increase between 2017 and 2024 was 17.0%. On the other hand, the marked value added to equity (MVA_E) decreased steadily until 2019, and the deep collapse is not the lockdown period, but the years 2022–2023. These two years represent a market value loss (MVL) of PLN -104.7 bn, compared to the creation of PLN 270.9 bn for the period 2017–2024. Finance companies reacted in a strongly negative way to the lockdown, whereas the slump in production companies emerged only after 2021. Meanwhile, commerce companies recorded a positive MVA_E throughout.

In general, the increase in dMV_E between 2017 and 2024 is PLN +111.0 bn (+19.4%), and yet the loss of $dMVA_E$ amounting to PLN -80.1 bn is a negative assessment and a strong signal to investors (shareholders). Production companies lost the most (PLN -118.3 bn) (Figure 1).

A weakness of MVA_E is its failure to take into account the expectations of shareholders. This is because the creation of added value may be progressing, but the return on investment is below their expectations. The application of the proposed measure of excess market value added, taking into account these expectations, first requires checking that it does not distort market information (verification of hypothesis H1).

For H1 verification, two pairs of correlations were examined: dMV_E and $dMVA_E$, and dMV_E and MVA_{EN} . The correlation was expected to be very high (0.7–0.9). The Williams test generally showed a very high, positive and statistically significant correlation, $T2 = 0.794$ (as an average for 30 companies, for each p-value < 0.000, min = 0.646, max = 0.950). The highest degree of correlation was for production companies ($T2 = 0.838$), followed by commerce ($T2 = 0.764$) and finance ($T2 = 0.729$).

The above is the basis for accepting the first hypothesis as true: $H1_0$ – excess market value added to equity is correlated with changes in company capitalisation to a similar extent as increases in market value added. This means that MVA_{EN} is an appropriate, non-deformative measure suggested for use in assessing the effectiveness of shareholder value creation, taking into account shareholder expectations.

4.2. Expected versus real value creation

The demonstrated loss of market value added to equity (MVA_E) between 2017 and 2024 of PLN -80.1 bn, is not the end of the negative assessment. In fact, the size of the value gap as measured by excess market value added to equity (MVA_{EN}) was PLN -369.1 bn (4.6 times larger). The shareholders expected such value creation. Unfortunately, not only were their expectations not met (the condition is $MVA_{EN} = 0$), but there was a significant gap ($MVA_{EN} < 0$).

The relative size of this gap (MVA_{EN} to IC_E^C ratio) as an average for 2017–2024 was -1.4%, while relative to stock market capitalisation (MVA_{EN} to MV_E ratio) it was -10.3%.

In view of the creation of market value added to equity (MVA_E) that was in place since 2017, investor expectations also gradually weakened and thus the value gap narrowed. The 2020 pandemic and the accompanying deeply pessimistic sentiment and low expectations did not translate into dramatically poor company performance, and the gap narrowed in the second half of 2020 on that account. It was different in 2022. Instead of the expected rapid rebound, there was a post-pandemic recession due to the dislocation of the global economy and the value gap widened (Figure 2).

Between 2017 and 2024, the largest MVA_{EN} value gap (PLN -139.6 bn) appeared in finance companies (37.8% share of the total gap), followed by production (PLN -127.1 bn, 34.4%) and trade (PLN -102.3 bn, 27.7%). Differences between these types of business were not significant in the period under review, except 2022 and especially 2024 – in finance (PLN -30.6 bn) twice as high as in commerce and half as high as in production.

To verify hypothesis H2, the correlation of MVA_E and $dMVA_{EP}$ was examined. A result close to unity was expected. The resulting $r = 0.192$ is a near-poor correlation (as an average for 30 companies, for each p-value < 0.000 , min = 0.059, max = 0.299, sd = 0.066). The result is also not significantly improved by correlation studies using higher-degree polynomials.

The above is the basis for rejecting the second hypothesis as null hypothesis H_{2_0} and accepting the alternative hypothesis H_{2_1} : the degree of market value added creation by WSE WIG30 companies between 2017 and 2024 was insufficient in terms of shareholders' expectations.

4.3. Properties of a set of companies: ranking and classification

For the measure of MVA_{EN} (as excess or value gap), a comparable measure is the change (increase/decrease) in the value-added $dMVA_E$. These values can be analysed as a distribution over time and companies.

Between 2017 and 2024, there was a dispersion and displacement of companies in the coordinate system ($dMVA_E$; MVA_{EN}). The value of the dispersion measure (DM) increased 2.1 times and its changes were weakly, positively correlated with the stock market capitalisation (MV_E) ($r = 0.145$). Until 2019, the DM remained stable, with the first spike occurring in 2020 (lockdown), but the highest in 2022 (also the highest amplitude of change) (Figure 3a). Increasing dispersion means that companies are moving away from each other, diversifying. The focal point moved deeper into the quadrant ($+dMVA_E$; $-MVA_{EN}$). What was significant was the displacements of companies in the least unfavourable direction, that is, into the quadrant ($-dMVA_E$; $-MVA_{EN}$). Therefore, in general, there was not only a loss of added value, but also an increase in the gap between expected and real results (Figure 3b).

Between 2017 and 2024, positive $dMVA_E$ (PLN +107.6 bn) were associated with 16 companies (six finance, seven production, three commerce) and negative values with 14 companies (PLN -187.7 bn, nine production, three commerce, two finance). On the contrary, in terms of MVA_{EN} , no company achieved a positive result (Figure 4).

Of the top ten companies representing positive $dMVA_E$ values, only one made it into the top ten in terms of MVA_{EN} – this was Bank Handlowy w Warszawie SA (BHW). It was ranked 10th on both lists of tops. Dino Polska SA (DNP) was characterised by the greatest value creation, while LW Bogdanka SA (LWB) had the smallest value gap. There were three companies in the last ten both in terms of $dMVA_E$ and MVA_{EN} , namely KGHM Polska Miedź SA (KGH), Allegro.eu SA (ALE) and Polski Koncern Naftowy Orlen SA (PKN). The latter recorded the largest loss of $dMVA_E$, while Allegro.eu SA showed the largest MVA_{EN} value gap among all companies (Table 1).

The data in Table 1 can be used as a basis for classifying the companies surveyed. They express absolute and cumulative results. Therefore, the classification has been improved by calculating the average rank position (ARP) in consecutive monthly periods within a given year and the variability of rank position (VRP), taking the standard deviation as its measure. In general, the ranking procedure eliminates the impact of outlier observations.

Firstly, ARP indicates that the companies differed more in terms of MVA_{EN} than $dMVA_E$. The gap between maximum and minimum for MVA_{EN} was 28.5 : 2.6, while for $dMVA_E$ it was 18.2 : 12.6. For only three companies did proximity to the ARP occur: Cyfrowy Polsat SA (CPS), Alior Bank SA (ALR) and Bank Millennium SA (MIL) (Figure 5a). Within the group of production companies, the ARP for $dMVA_E$ was the highest, as was the split. In contrast, commerce companies had the lowest ARP and financial companies the smallest split. In terms of MVA_{EN} , the highest ARP was achieved by finance companies and the lowest by production companies, with the split being the largest for the latter.

Secondly, the variability of rank position (VRP) was almost 2.5 times higher in terms of $dMVA_E$ (8.3) than of MVA_{EN} (3.4). A group of companies with a relatively low but persistent MVA_{EN} gap became apparent:

- Ten Square Games SA (TEN),
- Grupa Kęty SA (KTY),
- Asseco Poland SA (ACP),
- LiveChat Software SA (LVC),
- LW Bogdanka SA (LWB),

and with a relatively high and also persistent MVA_{EN} gap:

- Powszechny Zakład Ubezpieczeń SA (PZU),
- Bank Pekao SA (PEO),
- PKO BP SA (PKO),
- Pepco Group N.V. (PCO),
- Polska Grupa Energetyczna SA (PGE),
- Allegro.eu SA (ALE),
- mBank SA (MBK),
- Polski Koncern Naftowy Orlen SA (PKN),
- KGHM Polska Miedź SA (KGH),
- Santander Bank Polska SA (SPL).

The situation in terms of $dMVA_E$ was different (Figure 5c). The highest VRP in terms of $dMVA_E$ was recorded in the case of commerce companies and the lowest for production companies. Conversely, the VRP for MVA_{EN} was also highest for commerce companies, but lowest for finance companies.

Thirdly, by combining the relevant pieces of information concerning the ARP, a group of companies can be identified with a high (above average) position in terms of the creation of the $dMVA_E$ value and at the same time a high (above average) position in terms of the low MVA_{EN} value gap (quadrant I). Similarly, quadrant II consists of a group of companies with a low (below average) position in terms of $dMVA_E$ and a simultaneous low (below average) position in terms of MVA_{EN} . These are two groups with opposite characteristics. The next two groups (quadrants) represent companies with mixed characteristics (Figure 5b).

Quadrant I includes companies such as:

- Asseco Poland SA (ACP),
- AmRest Holdings SE (EAT),
- Alior Bank SA (ALR),
- Grupa Kęty SA (KTY),
- CCC SA (CCC),
- Orange Polska SA (OPL),
- Kruk SA (KRU),
- LiveChat Software SA (LVC),
- Ten Square Games SA (TEN),
- Bank Handlowy w Warszawie SA (BHW).

Quadrant II includes companies such as:

- mBank SA (MBK),
- Pepco Group N.V. (PCO),
- Polska Grupa Energetyczna SA (PGE),
- Powszechny Zakład Ubezpieczeń SA (PZU),
- Cyfrowy Polsat SA (CPS),
- Polski Koncern Naftowy Orlen SA (PKN),
- Bank Pekao SA (PEO),
- KGHM Polska Miedź SA (KGH),
- PKO BP SA (PKO),
- Allegro.eu SA (ALE).

4.4. Company profiles

Continuing the theme of looking for characteristics of companies within their cluster, the similarity of structures was studied using the taxonomic measure of similarity (TMS) as an assessment of the profiles. This measure determines the difference in structures over time, simultaneously, in terms of two quantities, i.e. $dMVA_E$ and MVA_{EN} , for two of their measures: ARP and VRP.

On a monthly basis, the TMS measure for ARP showed weak growth until 2020, while more pronounced declines occurred in 2021 and 2023. Therefore, in these two years, there was a significant diversification of companies in terms of their structures, those structures being significantly different

from the previous year's. The correlation with the stock market capitalisation (MV) was inversely related but weak ($r = -0.167$). The correlation with the density measure (DM), on the other hand, was positive but weak ($r = 0.082$). However, in the three years 2020, 2022 and 2024, the strong increases in dispersion were accompanied by some increase in similarity, so that the companies, while increasing their differences from each other in terms of value creation and its volatility, maintained similar structure relationships to each other.

In general, the similarity of the structures was low (0.68–0.74), the lowest for production companies, slightly higher for companies in commerce and finance in 2021 (Figure 6a). On the contrary, in 2021 the TMS for VRP was higher (+7.8 points, +0.0%) than for ARP, the highest for production companies and the lowest for commerce (Figure 6b).

The above findings are the basis for rejecting the third hypothesis as the null hypothesis $H3_0$, accepting the alternative hypothesis $H3_1$: the value creation profiles of the companies under study in terms of market value added to equity and excess market value added to equity are not similar.

In assessing the characteristics of companies (also their classification), it is also worth using the relationship between the standard deviation (SD) and the value creation, $dmVA_E$. The standard deviation expresses the volatility and thus the risk to value creation. The calculated relationship (RVC, risk-value creation) therefore illustrates how many units of risk correspond to a unit of value creation.

In the value-creating company group (positive $dmVA_E$) combined for the period 2017–2024 (as a balance), the lowest risk burden fell on Asseco Poland SA (ACP), Grupa Kęty SA (KTY) and Dino Polska SA (DNP). The above-average risk burden (> 0.34), on the other hand, was borne by five companies, including AmRest Holdings SE (EAT), with up to 1.60 units of risk per unit of value creation.

In the group of companies with impairment (negative $dmVA_E$), it was Alior Bank SA (ALR) and Powszechny Zakład Ubezpieczeń SA (PZU) that carried the highest risk burden. In the former company, there were 1.15 risk units per unit of impairment. On the other hand, 10 companies had a below-average risk burden (< 0.32), and the lowest among them LW Bogdanka SA (LWB) and Jastrzębska Spółka Węglowa SA (JSW) (Table 2).

Taking into account the RVC criterion, among the companies included in the first quadrant (high positive rating against $dmVA_E$ and MVA_{EN}), Grupa Kęty SA (KTY) and Asseco Poland SA (ACP) draw attention with the lowest RVC values, followed by Bank Handlowy w Warszawie SA (BHW) and LiveChat Software SA (LVC). Among the companies classified in the second quadrant (high negative rating), a special place is occupied by General Insurance Company SA (PZU) with the highest RVC. In turn, Polski Koncern Naftowy Orlen SA (PKN), Pepco Group N.V. (PCO) and Allegro.eu SA (ALE) showed a low RVC, only slightly higher than the best companies included in the first quadrant in this respect.

5. Discussion

Declines in the stock market capitalisation (market value) of WSE WIG30 companies were already occurring systematically before the pandemic (2020). However, the market value added, which was in an even deeper downward trend, was still positive. This information created an inaccurate picture of the effectiveness of investments in company shares (Johnson, Kim, So 2020). This may explain the dysfunctionality of the efficient market hypothesis (EMH) during the pandemic, as well as

the expansionary monetary policies of central banks, affecting financial markets, with an apparent correlation between the growth of monetary aggregates and stock market capitalisation (Echarte Fernández et al. 2022). Only when a market value loss occurred in 2022, exacerbated in 2023, it was understood that the pandemic year, and the rebound afterwards, was only a temporary jolt to value creation, which otherwise, in an obvious trend, was heading towards showing losses.

The question is whether this signal was readable beforehand (Huang, Yang, Zeng 2020), and above all, whether it contained reliable information for investors and shareholders. The answer to both questions is embedded in the excess market value added to equity. It informed in advance of a persistent value gap since as early as 2017, a gap that widened significantly after the pandemic year (2020). At the same time, internal measures showed value creation. However, the market valuation was far lower, discounting future growth risks to a greater extent than company managers (Tarighi et al. 2023).

Undoubtedly, the type of activity has shown links to changes in market value. Finance companies (banking and insurance) suffered the largest value loss in the lockdown year. This was determined by factors specific to the sector (Demirgüç-Kunt, Pedraza, Ruiz-Ortega 2021). However, its added value has risen sharply, and in the last year they gained as much as in the seven previous years. Commerce companies at the beginning of the lockdown quickly implemented forms of on-line commerce (Kubiczek, Derej 2021), showing value gains. Production companies initially did not lose out, supported by a strong cash injection and the cover of intervention policies. Problems and depreciation came in 2022 and 2023 (cooling economies, disrupted supply chains) (Graves, Tomlin, Willems 2022), but the figures for the next year were already positive. However, these results are not conclusive. In fact, in terms of excess value, the value gap was persistent in 2017–2024 and affected all activities. Finance (37.8%) and production (34.4%) were the most affected sectors. In total, the cumulative excess market value added to equity (PLN -369.1 bn) represented 68.3% of the capital invested by shareholders and 64.6% of the market value of the WSE WIG30 companies.

The discussion should raise the issue of interpreting the performance of individual companies. This is because a positive excess value can arise with a negative real value, due to the negative expected value being even lower. This creates an ambiguous situation (Du 2019). Some authors consider this to be a kind of bonus (Malmi, Ikäheimo 2003). Such an opinion cannot be upheld, as it would mean discriminating against companies showing positive MVA_{ER} values, which is a paramount fact and a key measure in assessing value creation. In the course of the present research, the situation in question occurred in only 15 out of 2,880 analysed object-observations (a maximum of 4 out of 96 for a given company), not affecting the general conclusions drawn.

Excess value requires a specific supply of information, which is not a barrier for internal analyses. For external analyses, this means limiting periodisation to be no more frequent than quarterly. The high representativeness of the survey sample (39.4% WSE capitalisation) provides a strong basis for the general conclusions drawn. This article assumes that the market is the only arbiter that forms an objective opinion and discounts the capacity to create value in the future. This means that market assessment can underpin the appraisal of the effectiveness of value management by managers. Admittedly, such a stance may be met with polemics, which indeed is the case in scientific literature.

The present research has opened a new avenue in the analysis of value creation and will be continued. The possibilities of future venues to investigate involve researching companies from various industry indices and benchmarks.

6. Conclusions

In a turbulent period of change between 2017 and 2024, the readings of the weakening capitalisation of WSE WIG30 companies (17%) were not interpreted as strongly unfavourable. This perspective may have been misleading. At the same time, taking into account the invested capital, the market value lost was PLN -80.1 bn. However, this is not a final assessment either, as the efficiency of capital investment is its assessment through the prism of expected benefits. In this sense, there was a value gap measured by excess market value added to equity of PLN -369.1 bn, i.e. -11.4% relative to the invested capital.

In general, the simultaneous assessment of the effectiveness of value creation (achieving positive market value added) and its efficiency relative to the volume desired by shareholders displayed by WSE WIG30 companies in 2017–2024 is negative. In the present article, the adequacy of this assessment using the excess value concept has been examined in three steps.

In the first step, the research proved (the positive verification of hypothesis H1) that excess market value added to equity does not distort the content of the original information in the form of stock market capitalisation (market value). Although it is a more restrictive criterion, it faithfully reflects shareholders' point of view and their expectations.

In the second step, the research proved (the negative verification of hypothesis H2) that the degree of market value creation by WSE WIG30 companies between 2017 and 2024 was not sufficient in the face of shareholder expectations. This empirical verification is the basis for the negative assessment of both the effectiveness and efficiency of managers' value management of companies. These expectations were, in any case, tempered by the downturn, but it would have been desirable to ensure that the cost of capital invested by shareholders was at least covered.

In the third step, the research showed that the value creation profiles of WSE WIG30 companies in terms of market value added and excess value are not similar. This applies both to the rank position, to the power of creation, and to the volatility and risk per unit of value creation. The dissimilarity was identified both at the level of the entire sample and within the types of activity. In addition, companies classified as major value creators unfortunately failed to meet shareholders' expectations.

The results presented in the article and the general statements made above entitle us to conclude that the excess value research methodology has applications and use in expectations-based management.

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Appendix

Figure 1

Market value added to equity (MVA_E) of WSE WIG30 listed companies in 2017–2024 (quarterly data)

Source: research by the authors based on limited access databases (commercial databases): emis.com, notoria.pl, gpw.pl, stockwatch.pl, ekrs.ms.gov.pl. Available online:

<https://www-1emis-1com-1v9owocmt1833.hanbg.uek.krakow.pl/php/home>,

<https://uekr-1notoria-1pl-1y3wmvzmt1837.hanbg.uek.krakow.pl/companies/dashboard/WIG30>,

<https://www.gpw.pl/archiwum-notowan>,

<https://www.stockwatch.pl/gpw/indeks/wig30,sklad.aspx>,

<https://ekrs.ms.gov.pl/>.

For Pepco Group N.V., Allego.eu SA, Dino Polska SA, and Ten Square Games SA, regression-based imputation was used.

Figure 2

Excess market value added to equity (MVA_{EN}) and market value added to equity (MVA_E) of WSE WIG30 listed companies in 2017–2024

Notes: MVA_E – right axis.

Source: as in Figure 1.

Figure 3

Market value (MV_E) versus density measure (DM) for $dMVA_E$ and MVA_{EN} (panel 3a) and position of companies with respect to $dMVA_E$ and MVA_{EN} (panel 3b) of WSE WIG30 listed companies in 2017–2024

Notes: DM – left axis (dimensionless values).

Source: as in Figure 1.

Figure 4

Excess value added to equity (MVA_{EN}) and changes in market value added to equity ($dMVA_E$) of WSE WIG30 listed companies in 2017–2024

Notes: MVA_{EN} – right axis. Stock tickers were used to identify the companies (see Table 3).

Source: as in Figure 1.

Figure 5

Average rank position (ARP) of WSE WIG30 companies by excess value added to equity (MVAEN) and changes in market value added to equity (dMVAE): panel a) in 2017–2024, as a whole period; panel b) classification of the entire period 2017–2024; panel c) in 2017–2024, ‘heat map’, year by year

Figure 5, cont'd

Note: as in Table 1.

Source: as in Figure 1.

Figure 6

Profiles of WSE WIG30 companies in terms of taxonomic measure of similarity (TMS) for the ranking position (ARP, panel 6a) and its variability (VRP, panel 6b) based on the market value added to equity ($dMVA_E$) and the excess value added to equity (MVA_{EN}) in 2017–2024

Note: as in Table 1.

Source: as in Figure 1.

Table 1

Changes in market value added to equity ($dMVA_E$) and excess value added to equity (MVA_{EN}) of WSE WIG30 listed companies by rank position in 2017–2024

$dMVA_E$			MVA_{EN}			$dMVA_E$			MVA_{EN}		
Ticker	rank position	PLN bn	Ticker	rank position	PLN bn	Ticker	rank position	PLN bn	Ticker	rank position	PLN bn
DNP	1	26.9	LWB	1	-0.9	EAT	16	0.5	MIL	16	-8.1
PKO	2	17.5	TEN	2	-0.9	TEN	17	-0.4	CPS	17	-9.5
LPP	3	14.2	LVC	3	-1.5	ALR	18	-0.6	CDR	18	-11.1
SPL	4	10.1	KTY	4	-2.3	CCC	19	-1.5	PCO	19	-14.8
PEO	5	9.3	ACP	5	-2.4	PZU	20	-2.1	PGE	20	-16.1
MBK	6	6.4	ATT	6	-2.9	LWB	21	-2.2	LPP	21	-16.3
CDR	7	4.5	ENA	7	-3.5	ATT	22	-3.1	DNP	22	-16.7
KTY	8	4.4	TPE	8	-3.8	ENA	23	-3.5	MBK	23	-17.4
ACP	9	4.2	KRU	9	-4.1	KGH	24	-8.0	PZU	24	-19.9
BHW	10	3.2	BHW	10	-4.5	CPS	25	-10.0	PEO	25	-20.5
MIL	11	2.1	EAT	11	-5.2	PGE	26	-10.6	KGH	26	-22.5
OPL	12	1.4	OPL	12	-5.3	JSW	27	-12.1	SPL	27	-26.6
KRU	13	1.1	JSW	13	-5.4	PCO	28	-17.1	PKN	28	-33.9
LVC	14	0.9	CCC	14	-5.8	ALE	29	-31.4	PKO	29	-35.8
TPE	15	0.8	ALR	15	-6.9	PKN	30	-85.3	ALE	30	-44.6

Note: stock tickers were used to identify the companies (see Table 3).

Source: as in Figure 1.

Table 2

Risk charge on value creation ($dmVA_E$) of WSE WIG30 listed companies by rank position in 2017–2024

RVC (positive $dmVA_E$)			RVC (negative $dmVA_E$)		
Ticker	rank position	PLN/PLN	Ticker	rank position	PLN/PLN
ACP	1	0.06	ALR	30	1.15
KTY	2	0.06	PZU	29	0.93
DNP	3	0.08	CCC	28	0.56
LPP	4	0.13	TEN	27	0.53
BHW	5	0.14	KGH	26	0.30
PKO	6	0.18	PGE	25	0.21
LVC	7	0.19	ENA	24	0.15
PEO	8	0.21	ATT	23	0.13
SPL	9	0.23	ALE	22	0.12
MBK	10	0.29	CPS	21	0.09
KRU	11	0.31	PCO	20	0.09
OPL	12	0.36	PKN	19	0.09
MIL	13	0.41	JSW	18	0.08
CDR	14	0.42	LWB	17	0.08
TPE	15	0.80			
EAT	16	1.60			

Note: as in Table 1.

Source: as in Figure 1.

Table 3

Characteristics of the studied companies in the WSE WIG30 in 2024

Companies	Ticker	Assets		Equity		Revenues		Capitalisation		Business sector
		PLN bn	USD bn	PLN bn	USD bn	PLN bn	USD bn	PLN bn	USD bn	
Allegro.eu SA	ALE	20.2	5.1	10.4	2.6	10.5	2.6	35.9	9.0	E-commerce
AmRest Holdings S.E.	EAT	10.5	2.6	1.7	0.4	11.1	2.8	5.2	1.3	Hospitality
Asseco Poland SA	ACP	19.4	4.9	5.5	1.4	17.0	4.3	6.7	1.7	Software systems
Grupa Azoty SA	ATT	24.9	6.2	5.2	1.3	13.1	3.3	2.1	0.5	Chemical industry
LW Bogdanka SA	LWB	4.9	1.2	3.6	0.9	3.6	0.9	0.9	0.2	Coal mining
CCC SA	CCC	9.7	2.4	1.4	0.3	10.5	2.6	8.7	2.2	Footwear trade
CD Projekt SA	CDR	2.9	0.7	2.7	0.7	0.9	0.2	14.4	3.6	Computer games
Cyfrowy Polsat SA	CPS	39.0	9.8	16.8	4.2	14.2	3.6	7.8	2.0	Telecommunications
Dino Polska SA	DNP	12.1	3.0	7.0	1.8	29.5	7.4	37.7	9.5	Commerce
ENEA SA	ENA	40.3	10.1	18.0	4.5	30.9	7.8	5.5	1.4	Energy production and sales
Jastrzębska Spółka Węglowa SA	JSW	24.7	6.2	10.7	2.7	11.7	2.9	3.6	0.9	Coal mining
Grupa Kęty SA	KTY	4.6	1.1	1.9	0.5	5.3	1.3	7.2	1.8	Aluminium manufacturing
KGHM Polska Miedź SA	KGH	54.4	13.7	30.8	7.7	35.2	8.9	26.8	6.7	Copper mining
Kruk SA	KRU	11.4	2.9	4.6	1.2	2.2	0.5	8.4	2.1	Receivables management
LiveChat Software SA (act. Text SA)	LVC	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.4	0.1	2.0	0.5	Software systems
LPP SA	LPP	17.6	4.4	5.1	1.3	20.0	5.0	28.6	7.2	Fashion trade
Orange Polska SA	OPL	27.3	6.9	14.1	3.5	12.6	3.2	10.4	2.6	Telecommunications
Pepco Group N.V.	PCO	17.2	4.3	2.2	0.6	26.5	6.7	11.3	2.8	Commerce

Table 3 cont'd

Companies	Ticker	Assets		Equity		Revenues		Capitalisation		Business sector
		PLN bn	USD bn	PLN bn	USD bn	PLN bn	USD bn	PLN bn	USD bn	
Polska Grupa Energetyczna SA	PGE	109.7	27.6	51.8	13.0	63.2	15.9	16.0	4.0	Coal mining and power
Polski Koncern Naftowy Orlen SA	PKN	265.5	66.7	154.7	38.9	291.1	73.1	67.5	17.0	Oil refining
Tauron Polska Energia SA	TPE	48.1	12.1	18.5	4.6	31.2	7.8	6.2	1.6	Energy production and sales
Ten Square Games SA	TEN	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.6	0.2	Computer games
Alior Bank SA	ALR	95.7	24.1	11.3	2.8	8.7	2.2	11.9	3.0	Banking
Bank Millennium SA	MIL	142.4	35.8	8.0	2.0	9.9	2.5	10.8	2.7	Banking
Bank Handlowy w Warszawie SA	BHW	76.1	19.1	10.3	2.6	5.8	1.5	12.3	3.1	Banking
mBank SA	MBK	250.5	62.9	16.1	4.0	18.3	4.6	26.1	6.6	Banking
Bank Pekao SA	PEO	340.6	85.6	32.2	8.1	22.9	5.8	40.1	10.1	Banking
PKO BP SA	PKO	537.1	134.9	53.0	13.3	39.5	9.9	69.1	17.4	Banking
Santander Bank Polska SA	SPL	305.5	76.8	33.6	8.4	23.1	5.8	49.8	12.5	Banking
Powszechny Zakład Ubezpieczeń SA	PZU	518.4	130.3	31.8	8.0	64.6	16.2	38.0	9.5	Insurance

Note: Narodowy Bank Polski average USD/PLN exchange rate.

Source: as in Figure 1.

Rzeczywista a oczekiwana kreacja wartości rynkowej (spółki z indeksu WIG30 Giełdy Papierów Wartościowych w Warszawie)

Streszczenie

Problemem badawczym w artykule jest adekwatność zewnętrznego pomiaru kreacji wartości przedsiębiorstwa pod względem spełniania oczekiwań akcjonariuszy. Pierwszym celem jest ocena użyteczności zmodyfikowanej miary, którą jest nadmiarowa rynkowa wartość dodana. Oceną tą objęto jej związek z wartością rynkową (kapitalizacją giełdową) oraz rynkową wartością dodaną. Potwierdzenie użyteczności umożliwiło realizację dwóch kolejnych celów: ocenę stopnia ponadprzeciętności kreacji wartości i klasyfikowanie spółek oraz badanie podobieństwa profili pod względem pozycji rangowej dotyczącej siły kreacji wartości i jej zmienności oraz ryzyka – zarówno we wszystkich spółkach, jak i według rodzajów ich działalności.

Przyjętą perspektywą oceny jest kreacja wartości dla akcjonariuszy. Badania panelowe dotyczyły pomiaru kreacji wartości przez 30 spółek z indeksu WIG30 Giełdy Papierów Wartościowych w Warszawie w latach 2017–2024.

Sprawdzono trzy hipotezy:

H1 – nadmiarowa rynkowa wartość dodana dla akcjonariuszy jest dodatnio, silnie i istotnie statystycznie skorelowana ze zmianami kapitalizacji giełdowej, w stopniu zbliżonym do przyrostów rynkowej wartości dodanej dla akcjonariuszy;

H2 – stopień kreowania rynkowej wartości dodanej dla akcjonariuszy jest zgodny z ich oczekiwaniami, tj. minimalną oczekiwaną stopą zwrotu z zainwestowanego kapitału;

H3 – profile kreacji rynkowej wartości dodanej dla akcjonariuszy oraz nadmiarowej rynkowej wartości dodanej dla akcjonariuszy są podobne.

Proponowana miara nadmiarowej rynkowej wartości dodanej dla akcjonariuszy porównuje wartość oczekiwaną rynkowej wartości dodanej spółki z jej wartością rzeczywiście osiągniętą. Wartością oczekiwaną jest wartość przyrostu kapitalizacji giełdowej spółki uwzględniająca minimalną stopę zwrotu z kapitału własnego równoważną jego kosztowi. Wartość tego przyrostu jest pomniejszana o wartość zainwestowanego kapitału własnego. W badaniach zastosowano także narzędzia statystyki matematycznej, w tym niestandardowe, skomponowaną miarę zagęszczenia oraz taksonomiczną miarę podobieństwa.

Badania udowodniły, że zastosowana nadmiarowa rynkowa wartość dodana nie zakłóca informacji rynkowych i nadaje się do oceny skuteczności kreacji wartości dla akcjonariuszy. Wykazano również, że menedżerowie spółek z indeksu WIG30 nie spełnili wystarczająco oczekiwań akcjonariuszy. Zarządzanie wartością spółek zostało ocenione negatywnie pod względem efektywności i skuteczności. Ponadto profile kreacji rynkowej wartości dodanej spółek nie są podobne pod względem pozycji w rankingu dotyczącym siły tworzenia wartości, jej zmienności i ryzyka zarówno w zbiorze wszystkich spółek, jak i w ich podzbiorach według rodzajów działalności.

Barierą stosowania metody nadmiarowej rynkowej wartości dodanej jest dostępność informacji. Nie jest to przeszkodą w analizach wewnętrznych, natomiast analizy zewnętrzne mogą być prowadzone z częstotliwością najwyżej kwartalną. Dyskusyjna może być teza przyjęta w artykule, że tylko rynek dyskontuje zdolność tworzenia wartości w przyszłości, a zatem jego opinia może być podstawą oceny

skuteczności zarządzania spółką i jej wartością. Niejednoznaczność oceny spółki – pozytywna z punktu widzenia nadmiarowej rynkowej wartości dodanej wobec rzeczywistego ubytku wartości dodanej – wystąpiła w badaniach na tyle rzadko, że nie zakłóciła wniosków generalnych.

Analiza dostarczyła metody pomiaru kreacji wartości na potrzeby *expectations-based management* (EBM) uwzględniającej oczekiwania akcjonariuszy. Ponadto obiektywnie oceniono, czy wartość dla akcjonariuszy spółek z indeksu WIG30 jest jednocześnie tworzona i odzwierciedlona we wzroście wartości akcji spółek (kapitalizacji giełdowej) w stopniu wyższym, niż oczekiwali akcjonariusze.

Badania zmniejszyły lukę w metodyce obiektywnego pomiaru kreacji wartości z uwzględnieniem oczekiwań akcjonariuszy. Dostarczyły empirycznych podstaw do oceny stopnia kreacji wartości dla akcjonariuszy. Dotychczas nie przeprowadzono analiz o podobnym charakterze i zakresie zarówno na polskim rynku kapitałowym, jak i na rynkach zagranicznych. Metodyka badań ma wartość aplikacyjną i zastosowanie w EBM. Kierunek dalszych badań to analizy spółek z różnych indeksów branżowych oraz analizy porównawcze z odniesieniem do benchmarków.

Słowa kluczowe: wartość nadmiarowa, *expectations-based management*, kreacja wartości

